

Vol 3 Issue 4 May 2013

Impact Factor : 0.2105

ISSN No : 2230-7850

Monthly Multidisciplinary
Research Journal

*Indian Streams
Research Journal*

Executive Editor

Ashok Yakkaldevi

Editor-in-chief

H.N.Jagtap

IMPACT FACTOR : 0.2105

Welcome to ISRJ

RNI MAHMUL/2011/38595

ISSN No.2230-7850

Indian Streams Research Journal is a multidisciplinary research journal, published monthly in English, Hindi & Marathi Language. All research papers submitted to the journal will be double - blind peer reviewed referred by members of the editorial Board readers will include investigator in universities, research institutes government and industry with research interest in the general subjects.

International Advisory Board

Flávio de São Pedro Filho Federal University of Rondonia, Brazil	Mohammad Hailat Dept. of Mathematical Sciences, University of South Carolina Aiken, Aiken SC 29801	Hasan Baktir English Language and Literature Department, Kayseri
Kamani Perera Regional Centre For Strategic Studies, Sri Lanka	Abdullah Sabbagh Engineering Studies, Sydney	Ghayoor Abbas Chotana Department of Chemistry, Lahore University of Management Sciences [PK]
Janaki Sinnasamy Librarian, University of Malaya [Malaysia]	Catalina Neculai University of Coventry, UK	Anna Maria Constantinovici AL. I. Cuza University, Romania
Romona Mihaila Spiru Haret University, Romania	Ecaterina Patrascu Spiru Haret University, Bucharest	Horia Patrascu Spiru Haret University, Bucharest, Romania
Delia Serbescu Spiru Haret University, Bucharest, Romania	Loredana Bosca Spiru Haret University, Romania	Ilie Pintea, Spiru Haret University, Romania
Anurag Misra DBS College, Kanpur	Fabricio Moraes de Almeida Federal University of Rondonia, Brazil	Xiaohua Yang PhD, USA
Titus Pop	George - Calin SERITAN Postdoctoral Researcher	Nawab Ali Khan College of Business Administration

Editorial Board

Pratap Vyamktrao Naikwade ASP College Devrukh,Ratnagiri,MS India	Iresh Swami Ex - VC. Solapur University, Solapur	Rajendra Shendge Director, B.C.U.D. Solapur University, Solapur
R. R. Patil Head Geology Department Solapur University, Solapur	N.S. Dhaygude Ex. Prin. Dayanand College, Solapur	R. R. Yaliker Director Managment Institute, Solapur
Rama Bhosale Prin. and Jt. Director Higher Education, Panvel	Narendra Kadu Jt. Director Higher Education, Pune	Umesh Rajderkar Head Humanities & Social Science YCMOU, Nashik
Salve R. N. Department of Sociology, Shivaji University, Kolhapur	K. M. Bhandarkar Praful Patel College of Education, Gondia	S. R. Pandya Head Education Dept. Mumbai University, Mumbai
Govind P. Shinde Bharati Vidyapeeth School of Distance Education Center, Navi Mumbai	Sonal Singh Vikram University, Ujjain	Alka Darshan Shrivastava Shaskiya Snatkottar Mahavidyalaya, Dhar
Chakane Sanjay Dnyaneshwar Arts, Science & Commerce College, Indapur, Pune	G. P. Patankar S. D. M. Degree College, Honavar, Karnataka	Rahul Shriram Sudke Devi Ahilya Vishwavidyalaya, Indore
Awadhesh Kumar Shirotriya Secretary, Play India Play (Trust),Meerut	Maj. S. Bakhtiar Choudhary Director,Hyderabad AP India.	S.KANNAN Ph.D , Annamalai University,TN
	S.Parvathi Devi Ph.D.-University of Allahabad	Satish Kumar Kalhotra
	Sonal Singh	

**Address:-Ashok Yakkaldevi 258/34, Raviwar Peth, Solapur - 413 005 Maharashtra, India
Cell : 9595 359 435, Ph No: 02172372010 Email: ayisrj@yahoo.in Website: www.isrj.net**

MIGRATION AND GROWTH OF SLUM POPULATION IN PANDHARPUR CITY, OF MAHARASHTRA (STATE)

V.B.BANDGAR , B.T.NIKAM AND B.R,PHULE

Assistant Professor,Uma Shikshanshastra Mahavidyalaya Pandharpur.
Assistant Professor, Vijasinh Mohite-Patil Mahavidyalaya, Natepute.
Associate Professor , Songola Mahavidyalaya Sangola.

Abstract:

Slum and squatters are the major problems areas for urban environment slums in the cities of the world, particularly in developing country like India. Slums are developed they are illegally occupied houses and housing condition for the planning resources, and strategies are needed to address the problems of slum living condition. The slum dwellers in most of the cities are the mostly the migration from its surrounding areas and sub region of the village. Many planners are calling for slum improvement, particularly the commonwealth association of planners. When urban planners work on slum, they must cope with racial and cultural difference to ensure that racial steering does not occur. They are the people who provide service services to the city dwellers. But most neglected in terms of planning for their development. Slum is defined as the areas where people live on the government or private land having the civic amenities below the minimum requirements. the present paper is mainly based on the primary and secondary data .where ever it was essential, intends to study the migration pattern and growth of slum population in Pandharpur city in Maharashtra Pandharpur is one of the oldest, religious and pilgrimage and trade centers in India, which has flourished It is located on the banks of the Bhimā river,, it is a well known centre of its produce sugarcane on a large scale of the 23 slums 09 slums of Pandharpur city were selected for the present study and the data for which was collected through stratified random sampling technique to comprehend the migration pattern of slum population in Pandharpur city.

The slum dwellers have mostly migrated from the surrounding areas of the city and from the adjoining states mainly from Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan, and Bihar. It is suggested that the employment opportunities have to be generated in the area where from they migrate to check their migration to the city.

KEYWORDS:

slum, migration, housing condition employment, development.

INTRODUCTION

Migration is a form of spatial mobility of population between one geographical unit and another involving a permanent change of residence. The three components of population change. Migration holds a place of prominence than fertility and mortality. The pandharpur city has attracted for the migration on the rural background and areas because, the city can provide employment, education, health, facility. etc. to rural migrants who are largely unskilled and illiterate. The primary reason of rural-urban migration is economic background the rural poor migration in the cities search for employment. The rural population to the city is due to the pull exerted by higher average income and job opportunities, better health and housing condition for their families.

A large portion of the population that falls in to a low income bracket no alternative but to live in

improvised shelters. Which are devoid of even minimal civic facilities are known as slums Pandharpur city is a pilgrims city, last four decades usin city. These people are the facing to many problem in rural background social discrimination, drought, flood know action plan for disaster management etc. The key role of rural area migrant for know provide for basic facilities.

STUDY AREA

The area undertaken for the present study is the pandharpur city located in pandharpur tashil of solapur district lying on the Bank of Bhima river in south east Maharashtra it is located between coordinate 170 400 to 300 460 north latitude 750 190 to 360 380 East longitude's cover an area of 1303 sq.km and nature of area mostly lies rural. The study area has an elevation of 458 meter above the mean sea level total population of pandharpur city with population of 91,381 in 2001.

There are about 23 slums in pandharpur city out of which 22 are recognize and 01 slum are an recognize. These are 2457 slum houses. This constituted 8.71 percent of total 20942 household of pandharpur city in 2011.

There are, the present study intends to look in to the problem of migration form different areas and their concentration in pandharpur on marginalized areas.

OBJECTIVE

This paper aims to analyze the migration pattern of people livings in slums of pandharpur city and their growth rate.

DATA BASE METHODOLOGY

The study is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected by conducting the intensive field work in the slums of pandharpur city with the help of well planned and pre-tested household schedule through in interviews with the hand and other members of the family. The related secondary data was collected form the district census hand books, Socio-Economic abstract records of nagar parishad etc.

For collecting information regarding all aspects of migration pattern of slum population slum were selected employing stratified random sampling types. There are 23 slums in pandharpur city, out of them 09 were selected.

MIGRATION PATTERN OF SLUM POPULATION

Migration is the key process by the rural people belonging to certain socio-economic and religious back ground move to pandharpur city in to slum. With a view to obtaining a general picture of the process of migration in to the city a belief account of the immigrants and the areas slum dwellers arrived is given detailed analyzing of migratory people is based on the primary data collection by the household schedules form 350 slums household disseminated in 09 selected slums (Table 1)

Table No.1 Migration pattern of slum population in pandharpur, city 2011

Sr.No.	Migration pattern	No. of migrated Families	Percentage
1	Intra – District migration	150	60
2	Inter – District migration	72	28.8
3	Inter – state migration	28	11.2
	Total	250	100.00

Source: Compiled by author

1) Intra – district migration

Migration intra district of enumeration within district is called as intra district migration. Out 250 served house holds 150 (60 %) families belonging to intra district migration.

People from the surrounding depressed areas have migrated to slum in pandharpur city. The high proportion (58%) of migrants is mainly form Barshi tashil and lowest (1.5 %) in North and South Solapur tashil.

2) Inter district migration

Migration form one district to another district is called inter district migration This type of migration constitutes 22.8 % in slum of the Pandharpur city. Kolhapur, Sangali, Osmanabad, Latur, Satara, etc. are the drought prone where from a large number of families are migrated to pandharpur and settled in the slum of the city. Most of them a working in construction sector as well as unskilled works and farming. The highest percentage of migrants has come form latur district (52.00) and lowest form Kolhapur district (2%) a part form Ratnagri and Raigad districts have also been found but their proportion very low.

3) Inter state migration

Migration form one state to another state is called as inter state migration. This type of migration is comparatively less of the slums of the pandharpur city. Only 11.2 % migrants other states of India to the city of pandharpur (Table-1). Some people are migrated from Karnatka, Rajasthan, Madya pradesh, Bihar, Andhrapardesh to this, city them 28 familes. (11.2%)

Table No.2 Intra - District migration to slum of Pandharpur city, 2011

Sr. No.	Name of the Slum	Name of the tashils and number of migrated families										
		Malsh iras	Sang ola	karm ala	Bars hi	Mad ha	Moh ol	Nand S.Solu pur	Akkl kot	Pandha rpur	Mangla weda	Tot al
1	Ambabai Patangan	1	2	2	4	1	3	1	1	3	2	20
2	Anilnager	1	2	4	7	2	1	1	2	2	1	24
3	Dnyanehwa nagar	2	1	1	9	3	2	2	3	1	3	27
4	Santh Peth	0	1	-	4	4	1	0	1	3	-	14
5	Koli Patangan	0	1	3	9	1	1	0	-	2	2	19
6	Akluj Naka	5	2	2	7	1	0	0	2	2	-	21
7	Solapur naka	1	3	-	2	-	-	1	1	1	-	9
8	Ambedakar nagar	2	-	1	1	2	1	2	0	1	-	10
9	Pandmavati tank	0	-	-	3	-	2	1	0	-	2	8
	Total	12	12	13	46	13	11	8	10	15	10	150

Source: Compiled by author

Table No - 3**Inter - District migration of slums in Pandharpur city 2011**

Sr. No.	Name of Slum	Name of the districts and number of migated familes							
		Solapur	Osman abad	Lat ur	San gali	Sat ara	Kolha pur	Ratn agri	To tal
1	Ambabai Patangan	3	2	7	1	2	2	-	17
2	Anilnager	2	3	2	3	-	-	-	10
3	Dnyanehwarnagar	-	2	3	1	2	-	-	8
4	Santh Peth	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	2
5	Koli Patangan	4	1	4	2	-	-	-	11
6	Akluj Naka	1	1	3	1	-	-	-	6
7	Solapur naka	2	1	1	1	-	-	-	5
8	Ambedakar nagar	-	2	2	-	1	-	2	7
9	Pandmavati tank	-	3	2	1	-	2	-	6
	Total	12	15	25	10	6	2	2	72

Source:

Compiled by
author**Table No - 4****Inter - District migration of Slums in Pandharpur city 2011**

Sr.No.	Name of Slum	Name of the State and number of migated familes					
		Karnat ka	Andra Pardesh	Rajast han	Bhi ar	Madhya Prdesh	Tot al
1	Ambabai Patangan	2	2	1	-	1	6
2	Anilnager	-	1	2	-	-	3
3	Dnyanehwarnagar	-	-	-	-	-	0
4	Santh Peth	-	4	-	-	-	4
5	Koli Patangan	3	1	-	-	-	5
6	Akluj Naka	1	-	-	-	-	1
7	Solapur naka	-	-	2	-	-	2
8	Ambedakar nagar	4	1	-	2	-	7
9	Pandmavati tank	1	-	-	-	-	1
	Total	12	8	5	2	1	28

Source: Compiled by author

GROWTH OF SLUMS

In pandharpur city emergence of slum is started since starting the last four decades. e.g Koli Pentagon, ambasbai pentagon, Anil nagar, and Ambadekar nagar are relatively improved slum formed between 1970 and 1980 most of these slums have developed on the government land. The slum in pandharpur city in Bhosale Chock (koli Pentagon) is development on Nagar parishad land.

During the 1971-71 another 4-5 slum are developed in different part of pandharpur city. Those include Solapur naka, Dhaneshwar nagar, Anil nagar etc. during 1999-91 fastly growth in slums for pandharpur city such as padmavati tanks, school No-9, Santh Pets etc.

Amonge these 23 slums, 22 slums are declared as legal or recognized and only 1 slum is illegal or un recognized to be notified. These unrecognized slums have been developed on private land.

Thus, the rapid growth of slum6 in Pandharpur city ongoing to a heavy influence of immigrants has led to growth of slums slum can for mulation can never be stopped unless rural. Poverty problem. High growth of population and slum dwellers in cities are just a shift of rural poverty to urban centers of the various city in India.

Table No5. Decadal growth of slums and slum population in Pandharpur.

Sr.No.	Year	No.of slums	Total Population	Decadul growth rate of slum population	Decadal growth rate of slums.
1	1981	07	1296	-	-
2	1991	13	5270	30.66	46.15
3	2001	22	14384	73.24	69.23
4	2011	23	19178	33.32	33.32

Source: Records of Pandharpur Nagar Parishad office.

Fig. 1: Growth of Slums in Pandharpur city (1981-2011)

GROWTH OF SLUM POPULATION

The term growth of population is used in it's broadest connotation to cover change in population numbers in habiting a territory during a specific period of time; irrespective of the fact whatever the change is positive or negative. This growth can be measured both in terms absolute number and percentage. The absolute growth is obtained by subtracting the population of an earlier date.

Growth of population is the change in the number of people living in a particular area between two given points of time. Two points of time expressed described as the growth rate of population. Rapid population growth and lack of employment Opportunities pushed more people in to slums. In pandharpur city, the growth of slum population started in 1970-71, because in this year a severe drought occurred in Maharashtra a large number of rural people migrated on a pandharpur city in search of work. A part from this, some started construction work and others took ghelter in sugar industries.

In this city are the industries in their construction works, of private housing societies, shopping mallows, developing new road and other services. Woman from these slums works domestic materials servants the family occupied open space near high standard colonies. Women's are working as same maids.

Table number 2 Shows the absolute growth and decadal growth rate of slum population in Pandharpur city. The population of slums in pandharpur city is 1971 in 2011.

TableNo.6 Slum wise decadal growth rate of slum population in Pnadharpur city.

Sr.No	Name of the Slum	Population of concerned years				1981 to 1991	1911 to 2001	2001 to 2011
		1981	1991	2001	2011			
1	Ambabai patangan	095	395	633	811	75.94	60.25	28.12
2	Anil Nagar	326	590	1653	2270	80.98	180.16	37.32
3	Dhaneshwar Nagar	422	395	2495	2730	11.20	178.77	9.41
4	Santh peth	-	380	944	1225	00	148.42	29.76
5	Koli patangan	-	305	322	525	00	5.57	63.04
6	Akluj naka	105	125	182	270	1.09	45.6	48.35
7	Solapur naka	95	310	340	342	2.26	9.66	0.58
8	Dr. Ambadkar nagar	123	375	850	1100	204.87	126.66	29.41
9	Padmavati tank	-	340	570	729	00	67.64	27.89
10	School No.9	-	3275	975	1125	00	160.0	15.38
11	Gajanan Maharajas area	130	300	957	1180	130.76	219.0	23.30
12	1971 B Ram Bag	-	-	334	600	00	00	79.64
13	Umandi Patangan	-	-	509	709	00	00	39.29
14	Lakubai ground	-	-	194	325	00	00	67.52
15	Sunil chal	-	480	580	725	00	20.83	25.00
16	Mahapurche Badave	-	-	317	415	00	00	30.91
17	Shete petrol pump	-	400	567	820	00	41.75	44.62
18	Nama Nand Mahavaj	-	-	497	770	00	00	54.92
19	Kustrogi vasahat	-	-	081	225	00	00	177.77
20	Copest depo	-	-	507	925	00	00	82.44

MIGRATION AND GROWTH OF SLUM POPULATION IN PANDHARPUR CITY, OF

21	Gthigahate plot	-	-	432	560	00	00	29.62
22	Vitthal Nager	-	-	235	500	00	00	112.76
23	Suleman chal	-	-	-	540	00	00	00
Total		1296	5270	14384	19178	306.63	72.94	33.32

Source: Based an Pandharpur Nagar Parishad office .

If we see the decadal growth rate of slum population in the city, during the first decades (1981-1991) the growth rate was 30.63 % and annual growth rate is 3.06 % the second decades (1991-2001) the growth rate was 72.94 % and annual growth rate is 7.29 % the second decade's growth rate rapidly in very fast. In 3rd decades (2001-11) the growth rate was 33.32 % and annual growth rate was 3.3 %.

During first two decades the growth rate of slum population was very high because large number of people from drought – prone is as of Osmanabad, Latur and Solapur district surrounding tahsil e.g. Barshi, Sangola, Madha. Malshiras, Migrated to Pandharpur city in search of employment work.

During the decades of 1981-91 the growth rate of population was round in high Dhnyaneshwar nagar, (32.56 %) Anil nagar (25.15) and low population in decades Solapur naka (8.66%). The second decades 1991-2001 growth rate of population in high Dhnyaneshwar Nagar , Anil Nagar (8.61) and Gajanan Maharaja (17.34), Temple area (8.2) and low population in this decades kushthroggi vasahat (0.56). This type negative growth rate.

In the next decades (2001-11), the high growth was found Anil Nagar (11.83), Santh Pate (16.38), low population of growth rate Kushtroggi vahasath (1.71%), This decades growth rate of slum population has declined as the migration rate declined.

CONCLUSION

The Slums are found all over the city but it's major concentration is in the central part of the city. The pandharpur city is a high growth rate in migrate people in Anil Nagar in largest area in a pandharpur city. Most of the slum are the located on a governmental land (nagar parishad) some slums locate on private land. The spatial distribution of these slums indicates that most located it central or dwellers parts of the city. The Pandharpur city in largest slum population. On the Anil Nagar, Santh Pate, Dhnyaneshwa Nager, the lowest slum population in pandharpur city is a kushatroggi vasahat. The pandharpur city fascinated the migrants on rural areas because the city can provide the employment, education and basic facilities etc. to rural migrants who are largely for unskilled and unilliterate. The pandahrpur is a pilgrame city various temple on the city many peoples host on pandharpur city About 75 % percent people migrants of district are the various tahsil and 17-18 % people migrant an inter district and 5.7 % people migrants on a inter states. Growth of slums in the city is due to, caste and social discrimination, social classes, caste in rural areas. The rapid growth rate of slums in the city on going to a heavy in tax of in migration growth of slums. Growth of slums and population has begun in 1970 – 71 in this city. Because 1972 Maharashtra largely area in drought prone, employment and development of educational felicities in the pandharpur city. Some round in city and other rural area industry (sugar industry MIDC) to invite a large number of manual workers. The construction of private housing society, shopping malls, road construction and pandharpur is a pilgrim's city. So form 1970-71 on words gradual increase in slum population has taken place in pandaharpur city.

REFERENCES:

1. Hitesh saxena (2012) ; urban geography ; New Delhi; srishti books distributors.
2. Desai, A.R. and Pillal, S.D. (1970); Slums And urban Ration; Bombay: Popular Publication.
3. Husain M. (2003) ; urban Geography. New Delhi ; Anmol Publication.
4. www.pandharpur4u.in/
5. United Nations, 2007. The Millennium Development Goals Report
6. National human resource report.
7. www.google.com
8. www.slum population in /-India
9. www.google_slum_migartion population link uk.

Publish Research Article International Level Multidisciplinary Research Journal For All Subjects

Dear Sir/Mam,

We invite unpublished research paper.Summary of Research Project,Theses,Books and Books Review of publication,you will be pleased to know that our journals are

Associated and Indexed,India

- * International Scientific Journal Consortium Scientific
- * OPEN J-GATE

Associated and Indexed,USA

- Google Scholar
- EBSCO
- DOAJ
- Index Copernicus
- Publication Index
- Academic Journal Database
- Contemporary Research Index
- Academic Paper Databse
- Digital Journals Database
- Current Index to Scholarly Journals
- Elite Scientific Journal Archive
- Directory Of Academic Resources
- Scholar Journal Index
- Recent Science Index
- Scientific Resources Database

Indian Streams Research Journal
258/34 Raviwar Peth Solapur-413005,Maharashtra
Contact-9595359435
E-Mail-ayisrj@yahoo.in/ayisrj2011@gmail.com
Website : www.isrj.net